

FACTORS OF REASONABLE AND EFFICIENT USE OF LAND

Son of Mirzomurotov Maksudjon Farhad

Student on “land cadastre and land use”

National Research University “Institute of Engineers” mechanization of Tashkent irrigation and agriculture” Bukhara Institute natural resource management

Abstract: In this article, the multifaceted factors that contribute to the rational and efficient use of land, the fact that land management is an important issue for sustainability and socio-economic development with the increase in world population and urbanization, land use policy, technological advances, economic incentives, environmental aims to provide insight into optimizing land use practices through a comprehensive analysis of various factors such as environmental protection and public participation.

Key words: Natural resource, social, economic, environmental, rational and efficient use, recreation, productivity.

The need for rational and efficient use of land is primarily based on its unique characteristics as a natural resource. It is distinguished by the versatility of its use, the limited size, the inability to replace it with other resources, and the fact that it cannot be moved from one place to another. The use of land as the main means of agricultural production is possible only in combination with other natural resources in certain optimal proportions. In addition, the society's ever-growing demand for material and other types of wealth requires a careful approach to the use of land resources and their protection. The meaning of "reasonable land use" is a rather complicated and complex

concept. The rational use of land usually means a certain action of a person towards the land with a certain goal in mind. The methods and tools chosen to achieve the goal may be different, that is, different methods can be used to apply this concept to life. Therefore, it is not an imaginary process, but a previously studied, planned and organized process. Therefore, when talking about the content of the rational use of land at the state level, the means and methods of applying this concept are based on the economic laws of the development of the society, taking into account the laws of existence of the land as an object of economic and social relations and relations in this society. includes. In this case, the process of "reasonableness" determined in terms of land use, criteria and conditions adopted according to the rule is determined by one or another limitation. For example, land use may be pre-determined by a certain loss for economic efficiency, pre-determined by the necessary social efficiency. The main content of the problem of rational use of land is prof. M.A. Gedelman and P.S. Shevchenko explain that land resources should be involved as much as possible in the production of the national economy and their better use, restoration and protection of the resource. According to these authors, "The rational use of land is, first of all, to ensure the effectiveness of its use in social output in accordance with the purpose set by the state". In this case, the task of rational use of land is defined by them as follows: "Taking into account the usefulness of the interaction of land with other natural factors in the process of using land as a specific condition of any activity and as the main means of agricultural production, and land protection is to achieve the highest possible efficiency in doing".

Professor V.S. Shamanayev believes that it is necessary to clarify the economic results of the indicators of the level of land use, as well as the rationality of its use. Since the concept of rationality is always related to the purpose, the rationality of land

use means the appropriateness of the use of land in production and non-production. In this case, rational use of land is defined by him as follows: "The criterion of rational use of land is a set of scientifically based production and non-production requirements of society for land based on economic separation from land for non-agricultural purposes and constant improvement of soil fertility."

The concept of "reasonable" is the process of land use, while "efficiency" is the result of this process, i.e. its consequence in terms of the obtained effect (result). According to the sign of time, it is concluded that it is the initial syllable of the concept of "reasonable", that is, it is primary. But the "reasonable" use of land is possible only from the point of view of the given parameters of the full effectiveness of this process, which meets the multifaceted interests of society. Therefore, the "efficiency" of land use is the starting point arising from the needs of the realization of the many interests of the society, and its achievement is achieved at the expense of "rationalization" of this process by setting appropriate conditions and criteria.

Effective use of land is an economic category, but this concept, as a rule, is not limited to the economic or economic content of agricultural land. It also includes concepts of social, recreational and conservation efficiency. Each edge of land use corresponds to the appropriate way, defined types: social, economic, ecological and other efficiency. If we look at land use only on one side, then in practice it will be possible to achieve the highest result according to the specific type of efficiency corresponding to this considered side. In this case, the highest efficiency for a specific type is achieved at the expense of a decrease in efficiency for other types, because the requirements of other (remaining) aspects of land use are not taken as primary, initial conditions. . In other words, the highest efficiency of a specific type, when land use

is carried out under the conditions of the requirements of a single edge, is a private phenomenon.

Thus, the "rationality" of land use refers to the most desirable end result in terms of the accepted criteria of efficiency, which is, as a rule, economic, recreational, health, and ecological, or some other combination, but is necessarily the highest new efficiency that can be expected under accepted land use conditions. The rational and effective use of such land is both a condition and a result of systematic land use at the same time, that is, it is its only dual function.

The main drawback of the above-mentioned rules on the concept of rational and efficient use of land from special literature is that they are considered in a very narrow sense, mainly from the point of view of technological use of land, that is, from the second stage of the cycle of land resources recovery. However, this concept should be viewed in a much wider sense, precisely in terms of the cycle of restoration of land resources, that is, it is necessary to look not only at one, but at all three stages.

The "reasonableness" and "effectiveness" of land use exist not only at the stage of its direct use, but also, first of all, at the stages of its distribution and restoration. At the stage of distribution, decisions are made on the terms, limitations, and sizes of the country's land resources in each branch, each enterprise intends to use. It is these conditions that determine the necessary level of "reasonableness" of the intended land use from the point of view of the formed interests of the country, industries, and enterprises. Because the concept of "reasonable" is characteristic of multi-purpose land use, it means that in this case, a new efficiency of land use is created, which is not the highest, but the most optimal of the given conditions or restrictions. T

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